

A Comparative Study of Free Plagiarism Detection Software

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Abstract:

Plagiarism has become a major problem in the academic sector in the recent years . With the rise of technology it is becoming increasingly easier for Researchers to copy and paste the content from Internet without giving the credit to original author. This has led to a significant increase in plagiarism cases at Academic institutions. To combat this problem several measures have been implemented by Universities. which are being used to avoid plagiarism. The plagiarism detection software is one of these components which is being used to avoid plagiarism and research papers of high quality can be written.

Plagiarism detection software is essential for any academic institution or organization that values the integrity of its content. With the increasing availability of free plagiarism detection software, it is important to understand which ones are most effective and accurate in detecting plagiarized material. This comparative study will explore the features, accuracy, and usability of some of the most popular free plagiarism detection software available today. The aim is to provide a comprehensive evaluation so that readers can make informed decisions when selecting a tool for their own needs.

In the era of internet, there are two types of software available through which plagiarism can be detected first is commercial software & second is free of cost software available on the internet. We will discuss five free software in detail in this paper. The software compared in this paper are DupliChecker, Plagiarism Checker, Copy Leaks, Paper Rater & Quetext. These software have open access and are free to use software's but they work on some specific condition like some software have usage restriction on the number of days & some software allows certain words limit which can be used for free. These software are easily available on internet. This software are widely used in educational institutions and the comparative analysis of these tools in this research paper will help many educational institutions and researcher to understand there tolls in details.

Keywords: Plagiarism, Copy Leaks, DupliChekers, Paper Rater, Quetext.

Introduction:

Today's era is the era of digitalization and today we are surrounded by the internet, but in ancient time books were served as our primary source of information in which there was less risk of plagiarism, but today in the era of

internet, we display content on blogs or websites. If someone copies their content and uploads it on their website as it is, then it is called plagiarism.

Plagiarism is the representation of another authors' language, thoughts, ideas or expressions as ones' own original work.

Now-a-days, you can see increasing numbers of plagiarism cases in academic world. Plagiarism is considered as an academic crime. We all must be aware about various aspects of plagiarism which can be used to improve the quality of research and academic writings. Mostly copy- paste generation is notable problem of plagiarism. The person who actually creates the content is the legal owner of that content. In general, some people do this crime, knowing and some people commit it unknowingly, sometimes it happens by accident due to some kind of reason or less awareness about the techniques to avoid the scriptural rules. In many places, the work done by someone is presented without giving credit, which is the biggest reason for plagiarism. If we use the data of someone else's in our article and then referencing him in the reference list, with this technique we can avoid plagiarism in our work.

Research Methodology:

In this research paper we are using the method of comparative analysis. This paper is based on secondary data. By the method of comparative analysis, two or more similar things are seen, how they differ from each other and what they have in common. This method is used in many areas to better understand the similarities and differences between products.

Objective:

- To analyze the role of plagiarism in research.
- To analyze how to avoid plagiarism in research.
- To analyze free plagiarism detection software.

Types of Plagiarism:

Plagiarism comes in many forms, some more severe than others—from rephrasing someone's ideas without acknowledgement to stealing a whole essay. These are the five most common types of plagiarism:

- **Global plagiarism** means passing off an entire text by someone else as your own work.
- **Verbatim plagiarism** means directly copying someone else's words.
- **Paraphrasing plagiarism** means rephrasing someone else's ideas to present them as your own.
- **Patchwork plagiarism** means stitching together parts of different sources to create your text.
- **Self-plagiarism** means recycling your own past work.

Plagiarism Detection Methods:

Plagiarism can be detected either manually or using plagiarism detection software.

- Manual Detection was the only method which was available before the documents were available electronically. This method involves an exhaustive effort from the detectors and requires an unparalleled memory. This method was not very useful when the documents that needs checking are too many or if the original work is not available for comparison.

- Software Assisted Detection involves a number of tools, documents and software. It employs an automatic plagiarism detection method by comparing document simultaneously like areDupliCheker, Plagiarism Checker, Copy Leaks, Paper Rater & Quetext etc

Types of Plagiarism Detection Software:

Plagiarism detection or content similarity detection is the process in which one try to find out the similarity or copyright infringement of any document or content. In this process, one takes help of some software, which is called plagiarism detection software. There are mainly two types of plagiarism detection software: open access/freely available software and pay and use software.

This module is focusing mainly on two types of software:

- **Freely available software**
- **Commercial software**

Open access/freely available software:

These are the software(s) which anyone can use free of cost to check the content similarity or plagiarism in the written work. Few such software(s) are Dupli checker, Plagiarism Checker, Copy leaks, PaperRater, QueText etc., which are being used to check plagiarism with certain conditions. These open access or free to use software(s) work on specific conditions like some software allow to use freely for 15 days, some allow for one month, some allow for certain words limit, etc.

Commercial software: These software(s) are being used on payment basis. You have to pay to check the originality in your work. But there are some organizations which purchase the license of software as institution or organization and allow to individuals/members to use free of cost having user account with designation on it.

For example: INFLIBNET has subscribed URKUND and allows access to various universities and colleges freely through their libraries. Some institutions/universities have subscribed Turnitin for this purpose.

Open access/ Freely available software:

Dupli Checker:

This software is developed in 2006. This is free plagiarism detection software; this software can check plagiarism of up to one thousand words in an article at a time. It tells you in percentage how original your article is and how much plagiarized. Dupli checker is a good software to use for free which checks plagiarism in both English and Hindi language.

Plagiarism Checker:

This Plagiarismcheckr.com website is developed in December 2005 & Just one month after its creation, this site received its first review. Jeffery Hodges, the reviewer, is an assistant professor at Korea University. He is experienced in the battle against plagiarism. This software is user friendly and completely free plagiarism detection

tool by this software it can be easily checked whether the content is plagiarized or not. It is the most easy to use software and it also has easy step by step approach of plagiarism detection. This software is totally free.

Paper Rater:

This software is used for various purposes to detect plagiarism, today it is being used in more than 140 countries..Using this tool, you can also find out the mistakes of grammar and plagiarism can also be detected. This software has been created by communication experts and linguists, using which you can get results in a few seconds.

Copy Leaks:

Copy Leaks.com is developed in 2015 by Yehonatan Bitton, Co-founder and VP of R&D. It is a cloud-based authentication platform that enables you to track how e-learning content is being accessed over the Internet. This software works for various purposes like educational and commercial. For example, the business section addresses publishers and SEO agencies, while the education section addresses schools, students, and universities. The software is capable of scanning content in a variety of different file formats and languages. CopyLeaks is a great software that allows using API tools to search for stolen e-learning content all over the internet. It also offers a mobile app with an MS Office add-on that you can use to check for plagiarism while writing a document on MS Word. If you search for plagiarized e-learning material on this software, first you have to create an account on it. If you search for plagiarized e-learning material on this software, first you have to create an account on it and then you can find plagiarism on this software to the extent of free of cost.

Que Text:

This software is developed in 2000. It has a basic and functional interface that checks the Internet as well as various databases. It is completely free software that can be used easily and does not require any registration or account creation.

Conclusion :

Plagiarism has been a threat in the modern age for a very long time. Especially in the field of academic, in today's time there is more focus to find out about plagiarism in academic field. The birth of Internet technologies has made plagiarism much easier, but at the same time information and communication technology has also led to the creation of a variety of good quality software to detect such plagiarism. Which is available in today's time both in amount and in amount, using which people can detect plagiarism, this software is also beneficial for educational institutions, using which they can avoid plagiarism in the academic field and keep their academic records clean. In today's time, Plagiarism detection software plays an important role in detecting plagiarism, collecting information and writing something different from others and doing a good research, but some software used for free has a limitation. Only check plagiarism but all plagiarism software should be free so that plagiarism can be imposed properly and content can be made better. In short we can say that Plagiarism detection software is an important tool for anyone who needs to ensure that their work is original and free from any form of plagiarism. In this comparative study, we explored the features and performance of various free plagiarism detection software, in order to determine which, one provides the best value for money.

The results of this study showed that there are a number of good options available for those looking for a free plagiarism detection tool. Each tool has its own strengths and weaknesses, but overall they all provide a reliable method of detecting potential plagiarism in written works.

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